

THE IMPORTANCE OF MANAGERIAL PSYCHOLOGY IN THE TRAINING OF LEADERSHIP PERSONNEL

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Abstract: This article discusses the current features, problems, and pedagogical-psychological aspects of management psychology.

Key words: management, leader, management qualities, leader's leadership qualities, marketing.

For Uzbekistan, which is on the path of independent development, the issue of improving the management system, selecting, training, retraining, improving the qualifications of leading personnel, and creating conditions related to their higher level of knowledge is becoming an important factor of development. Today's realities show that it is not for nothing that the 21st century was predicted as the century of high information technologies and a sharp increase in intellectual level. This situation calls for reforms in the field of human relations, choosing subtle and unique ways of dealing with people of high intellectual level and effectively influencing them. If we take the example of Uzbekistan, it is the need of the time to form a layer of managers who are not free from the influences of world civilization and universal values, without losing the traditions of behavior, our national values, and our mentality.

There is a tradition of psychological assessment of leading personnel, development of a set of qualities necessary for them, and study of issues of correct selection of candidates in the field of social psychology. The seriousness and relevance of the scientific research carried out in this field has led to the emergence of an independent direction called management psychology. The personality of the leader is considered as one of the subjects of a number of disciplines - economics, labor sociology, management, marketing, etc. However, almost all of these researches acquire an explanatory and modeling character, and in fact, the process of selecting, sorting, changing (correcting) the leader's activity and adapting it to the requirements is based on socio-psychological principles. Unfortunately, the work carried out in this direction in our republic does not sufficiently take into account the requirements of building a civil society based on democratic principles.

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There is a tradition of psychological assessment of leading personnel, development of a set of qualities necessary for them, and study of issues of correct selection of candidates in the field of social psychology. The seriousness and relevance of the scientific research carried out in this field has led to the emergence of an independent direction called management psychology. As the main link (object) of management activity, the leader is considered one of the subjects of a number of disciplines - economics, labor sociology, management, marketing, etc., and each discipline studies its various aspects using its own methods and techniques. However, almost all of these researches acquire an explanatory and modeling character, and in fact, the process of selecting, sorting, changing (correcting) the leader's activity and adapting it to the requirements is based on socio-psychological principles. Unfortunately, the work carried out in this direction in our republic does not sufficiently take into account the requirements of building a civil society based on democratic principles.

President Sh.M. As Mirziyoyev noted: "It's one thing to be demanding about work, and it's completely different to touch people's personalities. Do not forget that people can obey you at work, they have equal rights with you in any other matter. ... We all know very well that our people are noble and honorable people. Our people can tolerate everything, but I say again and again, they cannot tolerate injustice and unfairness. A real leader, a real leader, is not appointed to test the endurance of people, but to create suitable conditions for them. Leaders at all levels - be it a minister or a governor, head of an office or organization, should be an example and example for everyone with their manners and culture." Management psychology interprets the relationship between the subject and the object of management during the implementation of tasks. In this regard, the organizational part of the system is characterized by the concept of obedience. The principle of obedience within management psychology is called subordination in management psychology. This expression implies the centrality of the system. The relations arising from the concept of subordination imply forms of obedience and execution in the behavior of employees of the organization. One of the main concepts in the science of management psychology is the subject and object of management. If we bring that process directly before our eyes, we can consider teachers as the subject of management, and students' activities as the object. Professional skills of the leader, acquisition of self-management skills, become one of the main topics in the management of employees and workers. We cannot deny that the concept of management psychology exists not only in organizations and enterprises, but also in a number of activity processes as mentioned above. It can be seen that the concept of management psychology is not only in the activities of the leader and employees, on the contrary, this concept is present in many activities. It is necessary to study management by connecting it with the economic basis of society, taking into account two organizational-technical and socio-economic aspects of management. Organizational and technical management is distinguished by the division of labor and cooperation in the preparation of products to obtain a clear consumer value. Socio-economic management is related to the existing production relations and defines management goals. Organizational and technical management is a type of activity that allows creating conditions for increasing labor productivity and production efficiency. The purpose of socio-economic management is to create conditions for workers to work effectively, to form a reliable national system of their

social protection, to ensure employment and to support the disadvantaged sections of the population. Management relations are an integral part of socio-economic relations and have various economic, organizational, social, labor, psychological and other forms. Management relationships represent a complex set of communication and interaction between subordinates, therefore, management is primarily the management of people.

The emergence and formation of management as a science, a field of scientific research, a response to the needs of big business, an attempt to use the advantages of the technology created during the industrial revolution, was the achievement of a few curious people who were eager to find the most efficient ways of doing work. Today, the models and methods of management science are used to solve the following issues: managing traffic flows in cities and optimizing traffic schedules at airports, creating work schedules for classes and auditoriums at universities, managing inventory in supermarkets and department stores, producing new types of products, and costing for advertising various products. It is effective in distribution, planning of material supply, distribution of equipment and labor resources for the production of various products in the factory, drawing up a schedule. Just as it cannot be directly experienced, it is impossible to observe a phenomenon that does not exist and will never happen. However, many leaders are bound to see only what is real and tangible, and this, in turn, is reflected in their focus on what can be seen. Modeling is the only systematized way to see the options of the future and determine the potential consequences of alternative decisions by the present time. David B. Hers stated: "A leader must choose the best available alternative to allocate his resources, determine the order of actions for himself and others, and attract new people and material resources. To do this, he must believe in the definition of the characteristics and stability of the environment in which the consequences of decisions will appear in the short and long term future. He must imagine all the uncertainty of this inevitable and unpredictable environment at the same time." Management science models are highly adapted to these goals and, as powerful analytical tools, allow solving many problems related to decision-making in complex situations. The founders of management theory are Taylor, Ford, Gilbert, Emerson, Fayol and others. Historically, the initial direction of management theory was called the "classical" (traditional) school. American engineer and researcher Frederic Taylor contributed greatly to the creation of this school. Taylor held all levels of the service ladder - from junior clerk to manager of a large metallurgical enterprise in the USA (Bestlegem).

He was one of the first to apply a scientific approach to the organization of some production processes and management of the entire enterprise. His famous works such as "Fundamentals of scientific enterprise management", "Principles and methods of scientific organization of management", "Administrative and technical organization of industrial enterprises" laid the foundation for a large collection of literature on scientific organization of production management published abroad. Taylor justified the need for a special functional management of labor processes, in addition to physical labor, the organization of production, along with physical labor, was tried to be divided into structural elements, and it was impossible to work in a hurry, in a hurry, everything was done in advance, all conditions and methods of work were predetermined. clearly defined. Management is to interest people in conscious labor and entrepreneurship, to control their responsibility for work, to ensure that their knowledge and skills have a positive effect on activity, and to organize incentives. This subject also consists of a set of theoretical and practical aspects that represent the forms and methods of organizing

management at all levels of economic management. A leader who has mastered management methods and knows how to use them effectively has a great impact not only on production, but also on the development of the entire economy. The most important task of today, says First President Islam Karimov, "is thinking in a new way in all areas of our life, especially in management, at the republican level, in the management of regions, districts, villages and neighborhoods, in the management of network links, and in difficult times. , is to find people who are able to keep pace with life, have pure faith, knowledgable, and business people, and give them confidence."

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